

Synthesis of Coumarins from Phenols and β -Ketonic Esters using Phosphorus Pentoxide. Part I.
Coumarins from Resorcinol and Ethyl Acetoacetates.

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From a study of the literature on the subject of synthesis of coumarins and chromones from phenols and β -ketonic esters, it appears that Pechmann's method* of the synthesis of coumarins in the presence of sulphuric acid and Simonis' method† of synthesising chromones in presence of phosphorus pentoxide have been accepted as of general application and any contrary view has always met with opposition.

In contradiction to Simonis' observation (Petschek and Simonis, *loc. cit.*) that ethyl acetoacetate did not lead to any definite product, the author, during the course of his attempts to synthesise different hydroxychromones, condensed resorcinol and ethyl acetoacetate in presence of phosphorus pentoxide obtaining a compound (m.p. 185°) identical with β -methylumbelliferone of Pechmann. The complete identity of the two products is established by their mixed melting points, as also by those of their acetyl derivatives. This raises a question about the general applicability of Simonis' method of synthesising chromones; and as such a detailed study of the reaction has been made with regard to various mono-, di- and tri-hydric phenols and β -ketonic esters. The present paper embodies the results of conden-

* Pechmann and Duisberg, *Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2119; Pechmann and Cohen, *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 2187; Pechmann, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 3681; Pechmann and Hanke, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 354; Pechmann and Kraft, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 421; Pechmann and Graeger, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 378; Biginelli, *Gazzetta*, 1895, 24, ii, 492; Dey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1606; Held, *Compt. rend.*, 1893, 116, 720; Fries and Klostermann, *Annalen*, 1908, 362, 3; Naik, Desai and Desai, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 83; Sen and Basu, *ibid.*, 1928, 5, 467; Sen, *ibid.*, 1929, 6, 1925.

† Petschek and Simonis, *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 2015; Simonis and Lehmann, *Ber.*, 1914, 47, 697; Simonis and Remmert, *ibid.*, p. 2229; see also Heilbron, Barnes and Morton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2569.

sations of resorcinol with substituted ethyl acetoacetates in presence of phosphorus pentoxide.

Simonis and Remmert (*Ber.*, 1914, 47, 2231) condensed resorcinol and ethyl methylacetoacetate in presence of phosphorus pentoxide and isolated a product melting at 262°, which they assumed to be identical with 7-hydroxy-2:3-dimethylchromone (m.p. 262°) previously obtained and described by Kostanecki and Lloyd (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 2948). Simonis maintained the identity of his product with that of Kostanecki without preparing and comparing the derivatives of his own product with those of 7-hydroxy-2:3-dimethylchromone. That his product is not identical with the chromone follows from the facts given below:—

(i) On repeating the experiment a product melting sharply at 256° has now been obtained, the melting point of which never reached 262° as claimed by Simonis and Remmert, even after purification by repeated crystallisations from different solvents.

(ii) The melting point of this product (m.p. 256°) was considerably depressed when mixed with a specimen of the chromone prepared synthetically by a slight modification of Kostanecki's method, which consists in heating 2:4-dihydroxyphenylethylketone with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate and subsequent hydrolysis of the acetylchromone.

(iii) Moreover it has been noted by Heilbron, Barnes and Morton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2569) that the compound prepared according to Simonis' method gives different derivatives from those obtained from the chromone of Kostanecki.

(iv) Also, the following table,

	I	II	III
	Simonis' compound.	Kostanecki's compound.	Pechmann's compound.
Original compound	m.p. 256° (262° claimed by Simonis).	262°	256°
Acetyl derivative	m.p. 165°	116°	165°
Methyl ether	m.p. 140°	126°	140°
Ethyl ether	m.p. 121°	124°	121°

shows that the compounds of set I are identical with those of set III, proving that the product (m.p. 262°) obtained by Simonis is identical with the one obtained by Pechmann and Duisberg (*loc. cit.*).

Thus the compound of Simonis is a coumarin and not a chromone, the derivatives of which are shown in set II.

Heilbron, Barnes and Morton (*loc. cit.*) having observed that the methyl group in position 2 in 2-methylchromones react with aldehydes in presence of alcoholic sodium ethoxide, attempted to condense the ethyl ether of Simonis' compound with aldehyde; but this being not a true chromone, the attempt failed. They sought to explain away this inactivity of the methyl group as due to the occurrence of the hydroxyl group in position 7. On the other hand 7-methoxy-2:3-dimethylchromone, prepared now by a modification of Kostanecki's method, is found to react readily, like other 2-methylchromones, with benzaldehyde to form a styrene derivative. Thus the explanation put forward by Heilbron and others falls to the ground inasmuch as the so-called chromone with which they started was really a coumarin.

That 7-methoxy-2-methylisoflavone prepared by Baker and Robinson's method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1981) has also now been condensed with benzaldehyde in presence of sodium ethoxide to form 7-methoxy-2-styryl-3-phenylchromone melting at 204° and identical with the compound prepared by Baker and Robinson by a different method (*loc. cit.*) is a sufficient proof of the view that the presence of the hydroxyl group in position 7 in a chromone is no hindrance to the reactivity of the 2-methyl-group. It is interesting to note that the isomeric compound obtained by Jacobson and Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1053) by the condensation of resorcinol and ethyl phenylacetoacetate does not react with benzaldehyde, thus affording an additional proof of their compound being an α -pyrone and not a γ -pyrone derivative as was claimed by them. The author thinks that the reaction with aldehydes is characteristic of the 2-methylchromones in distinction to the 4-methylcoumarins.

Some other substituted ethyl acetoacetates react with resorcinol exactly like the methyl compound to form coumarins irrespective of the condensing agent used.

In contradiction to the observations of Jacobson and Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 424) it has been found during the present investigation that a substituent in the ethyl acetoacetate molecule, however heavy or complex, does not in any way favour the formation of a chromone in the case of resorcinol even in the presence of phosphorus pentoxide, the formation of coumarins being instantaneous and complete.

On condensing resorcinol with ethyl benzylacetoacetate under different conditions Jacobson and Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 426) obtained two compounds melting at 186° and 224°, both yielding the identical acetyl derivative melting at 168°. On repeating the experiment the author obtained only the substance melting at 224° and failed to isolate the one, melting at 186° even after repeated attempts using sulphuric acid, phosphorus pentoxide and sodium ethoxide as condensing agents. Jacobson and Ghosh's explanation that the compound melting at 224° is an additive compound of the one melting at 186° with resorcinol has been now shown to be incorrect in view of the fact that the acetyl derivatives from both the compounds produce, on deacetylation, the compound melting at 224° and not the one melting at 186°. Hence it seems that their compound with m.p. 186° was an impure product and the one melting at 224° was 7-hydroxy-3-benzyl-4-methylcoumarin.

Resorcinol has also been condensed with acetonedicarboxylic acid in presence of phosphorus pentoxide to form 7-hydroxy-coumarin-4-acetic acid, previously prepared by Burton and Pechmann (*Annalen*, 1897, 261, 167). Incidentally it may be noted that coumarins are readily formed in the presence of sodium ethoxide as the condensing agent. Several cases have been studied with ethyl acetoacetate and its *C*-methyl and *C*-benzyl derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL.

αβ-Dimethylumbelliferone (7-Hydroxy-3:4-dimethylcoumarin) was prepared according to Pechmann's method (Pechmann and Duisberg, *loc. cit.*) formed colourless needles, m.p. 256°.

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared in the usual manner, crystallises from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 165°. (Found: C, 67.32; H, 5.30. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 67.24; H, 5.17 per cent.).

The *methyl ether*, prepared by means of dimethyl sulphate crystallises from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 140°. (Found: C, 70.55; H, 6.10. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.59; H, 5.88 per cent.).

The *ethyl ether*, prepared by the action of ethyl iodide in presence of sodium ethoxide in alcoholic solution crystallises in colourless prisms from alcohol, m.p. 121°. (Found: C, 71.39; H, 6.51. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.56; H, 6.42 per cent.).

The same *αβ*-dimethylumbelliferone is obtained by the interaction of resorcinol (10 g.), ethyl methylacetoacetate (10 g.) and

phosphorus pentoxide (35 g.). Vigorous reaction sets in in the cold with much evolution of heat. The flask is finally heated for half an hour on a boiling water-bath. The cold mass is treated with water and the brown solid is washed with water and crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) as colourless needles, m.p. 256°, the melting point being not depressed when mixed with a sample of α,β -dimethylumbelliferone prepared by using sulphuric acid.

The identical compound is also obtained with sodium ethoxide as the condensing agent. Resorcinol (4 g.) is added to a solution of ethyl methylacetoacetate (4 g.) in an alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide (1 g. sodium in 25 c.c. alcohol) and the solution heated for 15 minutes on the water-bath, when the sodium salt of the coumarin separates in quantity. The solution is then poured into an excess of water, acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the precipitate crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 256° (acetyl derivative, m.p. 165°, methyl ether, m.p. 140°, ethyl ether, m.p. 121°).

Preparation of 2:4-Dihydroxyphenylethylketone.—It is prepared by heating resorcinol (20 g.), propionic acid (17 g.) and zinc chloride (40 g.) for three hours at 140-60°. The red liquid is poured into ice and the pasty solid that separates out is repeatedly extracted with cold benzene, when long yellow needles separate as the benzene evaporates away. When crystallised from dilute alcohol, it is obtained as a colourless substance, m.p. 100° (yield 8 g.). Goldsweig and Kaiser (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891, 60, 447) records it to be a ruddy-yellow substance, m.p. 97°.

The *acetyl* derivative of the above is prepared by heating at 180° a mixture of the ketone (10 g.), acetic anhydride (40 c.c.) and anhydrous sodium acetate (10 g.) under reflux for 12 hours. The product is poured into water, slightly warmed and crystallised from dilute alcohol m.p. 116°. The acetyl derivative, on hydrolysis with sodium carbonate, gives the hydroxychromone (m.p. 262°) which on treatment with dimethyl sulphate produces 7-methoxy-2:3-dimethylchromone (m.p. 126°) (*cf.* Kostanecki and Lloyd, *loc. cit.*).

Interaction of 7-Methoxy-2:3-dimethylchromone and Benzaldehyde: Formation of 7-Methoxy-2-styryl-3-methylchromone.—The chromone (1 g.) is dissolved in the least quantity of absolute alcohol and an alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide and benzaldehyde (1 g.) are added to it. The solution is kept overnight, when on slight warming on the water-bath, crystals separate. These are filtered off, washed with rectified spirit and finally recrystallised from alcohol,

m.p. 152° (yield quantitative). (Found: C, 78.02; H, 5.55. $C_{19}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 78.08; H, 5.48 per cent.).

Interaction of 7-Methoxy-2-methylisoflavone and Benzaldehyde: Formation of 7-Methoxy-2-styrylisoflavone.—The 7-methoxy-2-methyl-isoflavone is dissolved in the minimum quantity of absolute alcohol and an alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide and benzaldehyde (1 g.) is added to it. Crystals separate out on keeping the solution overnight. The crystals are filtered, washed with alcohol and finally recrystallised from glacial acetic acid containing a few drops of water. Colourless needles, sparingly soluble in alcohol, m.p. 204°, (yield quantitative) identical with the compound prepared by Baker and Robinson (*loc. cit.*) by a different method. (Found: C, 81.2; H, 5.21. $C_{24}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 81.35; H, 5.08 per cent.).

7-Hydroxy-3-benzyl-4-methylcoumarin.—Phosphorus pentoxide (35 g.) is added to a mixture of resorcinol (6 g.) and ethyl benzyl-acetoacetate (10 g.). The mixture is heated for five minutes on the water-bath, when a vigorous reaction sets in. The flask is then immediately cooled under water and treated with water, when a viscous oil separates. The oil is separated, dissolved in dilute caustic soda solution, extracted with ether and the clear aqueous solution acidified. The heavy oil, thus obtained, is again dissolved in dilute alkali and precipitated with carbon dioxide. The brown solid is crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) as colourless prisms, m.p. 224°. (Found after drying at 120-30°: C, 76.27; H, 5.33. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 76.69; H, 5.26 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallises from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 168°, being identical with the acetyl derivative of the product melting at 186°, isolated by Jacobson and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*).

The *methyl ether* crystallises from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 119°, and is identical with the methyl ether of the product melting at 186° isolated by Jacobson and Ghosh. (Found: C, 77.01; H, 5.82. $C_{18}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 77.14; H, 5.71 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative, on deacetylation by boiling for an hour with 40% sulphuric acid, yields the original product melting at 224°. (Found: C, 76.21; H, 5.45. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 76.69; H, 5.26 per cent.).

The condensation of resorcinol (3 g.), ethyl benzylacetoacetate (5 g.) in presence of sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) according to Jacobson and Ghosh's method also yields the identical coumarin, m.p. 224°. The product obtained by the condensation in presence of

sodium ethoxide (1 g. sodium in 35 c.c. alcohol) of resorcinol (2 g.) and ethyl benzylacetoacetate (5 g.) also melts at 224°.

7-Hydroxy-3-ethyl-4-methylcoumarin was prepared from resorcinol and ethyl ethylacetoacetate in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid or phosphorus pentoxide. It crystallises from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 194-98°. (Found: C, 70.50; H, 5.92. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.59; H, 5.88 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallises from dilute alcohol in colourless prisms, m.p. 110°. (Found: C, 68.22; H, 5.75. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 68.29; H, 5.69 per cent.).

The *methyl ether* crystallises from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 93°. (Found: C, 71.51; H, 6.49. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.56; H, 6.42 per cent.).

7-Hydroxy-3-propyl-4-methylcoumarin was prepared from resorcinol and ethyl propylacetoacetate in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid or phosphorus pentoxide. In the latter case the mixture is heated for half an hour on the water-bath with a few drops of absolute alcohol; the pasty solid obtained on adding water is dissolved in dilute alkali, the alkaline solution extracted with ether and the aqueous solution acidified. It crystallises in colourless prisms from dilute alcohol, m.p. 169-71°. (Found: C, 71.32; H, 6.30. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.56; H, 6.42 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative, crystallises in rectangular plates from dilute alcohol, m.p. 119°. (Found: C, 69.12; H, 6.19. $C_{15}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 69.23; H, 6.15 per cent.).

7-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-4-methylcoumarin was prepared from resorcinol and ethyl isopropylacetoacetate in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid or phosphorus pentoxide as in the above case. It crystallises from dilute alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 224°. (Found: C, 71.58; H, 6.46. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.56; H, 6.42 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallises from alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 124°. (Found: C, 69.32; H, 6.21. $C_{15}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 69.23; H, 6.15 per cent.).

7-Hydroxy-3-isobutyl-4-methylcoumarin was prepared from resorcinol and ethyl isobutylacetoacetate in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid or phosphorus pentoxide. In the latter case the oil, separating on adding water is extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with dilute caustic soda and the aqueous alkaline solution precipitated with carbon dioxide. It crystallises from dilute

alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 153°. (Found: C, 72.22; H, 7.1. $C_{14}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 72.41; H, 6.90 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallises from dilute alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 109°. (Found: C, 69.91; H, 6.63. $C_{16}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 70.07; H, 6.57 per cent.).

7-Hydroxy-3-phenyl-4-methylcoumarin was prepared by adding phosphorus pentoxide in the cold to a solution of resorcinol and ethyl phenylacetoacetate in a few c.c. of absolute alcohol. The reaction is almost complete in the cold. It melts at 226° and its acetyl derivative melts at 185°, hence it is identical with the compound prepared with sulphuric acid by Jacobson and Ghosh (*loc. cit.*).

The *methyl ether*, prepared with the help of dimethyl sulphate and caustic soda, melts at 104° and not at 87° as recorded by Jacobson and Ghosh. (Found: C, 76.23; H, 5.42. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 76.69; H, 5.26 per cent.).

7-Hydroxy-3-chloro-4-methylcoumarin (m.p. 236°, acetyl derivative, m.p. 161°), identical with Pechmann and Hanke's compound (*Ber.*, 1901, 34, 354) is obtained by adding phosphorus pentoxide to a solution of resorcinol and ethyl chloroacetoacetate in a few c.c. of alcohol.

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